

Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine

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- The applied research grants, EPC-20-007 and EPC-23-024, fund the development of the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine which transforms the foundational climate and environmental data that underpins California's Climate Change Assessment into actionable information to improve electricity sector resilience. This platform provides users with customized data, advanced analytics, and powerful cloud computing resources, allowing users to perform high-level analysis without needing to download massive localized climate datasets. Enhanced metrics that convert climate data into electricity sector specific formulations and novel analytics direct users to the most relevant scenarios for their specific applications. The cloud-based data platform provides unprecedented computational resources to users, pre-loaded with easy-to-access capacity for the transformation of climate data into stakeholder identified formats, with supporting analytics guiding users to best practices and solutions for their specific application. Continual outreach provides foundational educational training and support to users of the data platform.

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Guidance Overview

The Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine facilitates access to California-specific climate data. It features tools to explore climate projections, models, historical data, global warming levels, and methodologies, all geared toward supporting informed decision making across sectors and utilizing the best available climate science.

The following resources will help data users better understand how the Analytics Engine tools can be utilized to achieve adaptation and resilience goals.

[About Climate Projections and Models](#)

An overview of climate projections and models. This section explains their generation, downscaling, validation, and incorporation of greenhouse gas emissions, along with details on historical data, global warming levels, and how the Analytics Engine tools enable users to explore these concepts.

[Guidance on Using Climate Data in Decision Making](#)

Comprehensive guidance on how to leverage climate data to inform decision making across sectors. This section will help data users enhance resilience and sustainability by anticipating and mitigating climate impacts using a series of climate data guidelines, best practices, and specific FAQs tailored to California's needs.

About Climate Projections and Models

The following sections provide an overview of climate projections and models, and how Analytics Engine tools have been developed to allow users to explore a variety of concepts. To learn more about the scientific methodology that underlies each of the following sections, please see the page titled References under the Guidance tab. To better understand how to apply these concepts to different adaptation and planning contexts, please see the Guidance on Using Climate Data in Decision Making page.

Topics covered in this section:

- What are **climate projections**?
- How are **climate projections generated**? What is a **global climate model (GCM)**?
- What is an **ensemble member**? What is a **model ensemble**?
- What is **gridded data**?
- What is **downscaling**?
- What **climate projections** and **GCMs** are on the Analytics Engine?
- How are **climate models validated**?
- What is **bias correction**?
- What **historical data** are available on the Analytics Engine?
- How are **greenhouse gas emissions** incorporated in climate models? What is an **emissions scenario**?
- What are **global warming levels (GWLs)**?
- What are **sources of uncertainty** in climate projections?

What are climate projections?

The data provided on the Analytics Engine are projections, or estimates, of potential future climates. Projections are not weather predictions and should not be treated as such. Weather is the short-term behavior of the atmosphere, and is characterized over time periods of days and weeks. Climate is the long-term behavior of the atmosphere, and it is characterized over multiple decades – it is the long-term statistics of weather conditions. The Analytics Engine provides users with the tools to characterize the long-term climate in new and novel ways, including how extremes may change in a warming climate. Climate projections cannot tell what will happen on a given date in the future, but they can describe the future climate more generally, e.g. how much warmer the typical July is likely to be or how much less snow will accumulate in the mountains in the average winter. Climate projections can also describe how much more often (or less often) extreme events such as heat waves and heavy rainfall are likely to occur in the future. While they cannot predict when these events will actually occur, they can give estimates for the changes in frequency and likelihood of these events occurring in the future.

How are climate projections generated? What is a GCM?

Climate scientists create projections of future climate using powerful tools called global climate models (often referred to using the technical name “general circulation models,” or GCMs). GCMs are complex computer software that crunch through thousands of mathematical equations to produce the most

accurate scientific representations of how climate works. Earth System Models (ESMs) are similar to GCMs, and incorporate additional physical, chemical, and biological processes to better represent climate. Many of the [CMIP6](#) models either are ESMs, or incorporate several elements of them. GCMs can be used to simulate climate over past historical periods and to run experiments in which scientists impose certain conditions on the model to see how the climate system responds. This can provide key insight to major environmental processes (e.g., the impacts of deforestation). A future climate projection is the product of GCM experiments in which scientists implement a plausible scenario of the future changes in the atmospheric concentration of greenhouse gases, anthropogenic aerosols, and, in some models, land use changes. What these scenarios are will be discussed further in the “How are greenhouse gas emissions incorporated in climate models? What is an SSP?” section below.

What is an ensemble member? What is a model ensemble?

A single climate model can be run multiple times, using slightly different sets of initial conditions. Each of these runs, or simulations of the future, is referred to as an ensemble member. Due to the chaotic nature of the Earth’s weather systems, starting from slightly different initial conditions leads to different weather outcomes for each ensemble member. By incorporating variations in this manner, ensemble members from a single model are able to capture the internal variability of the climate system. Users of climate data can benefit from these ensembles as they generate a range of plausible future outcomes and can help decision makers better understand planning impacts. To capture the full spectrum of potential future outcomes, it is crucial to examine multiple models and their available ensemble members - this is often called a model ensemble. Considering multiple models enhances the robustness of statistical analyses and enables characterization of extreme events. When performing such analyses, it is important to consider the model-to-model variability and the internal variability within each model. For users who require a comprehensive understanding of future climate projections, utilizing a diverse set of ensemble members across multiple models is recommended. Analytics Engine notebooks are intentionally designed to enable use of multiple models and ensemble members in climate data analyses. For additional details on how to make these selections, see the question “How should users choose between the large number of models and/or ensemble members provided in the Analytics Engine?” in the Guidance on Using Climate Data in Decision Making section.

What is gridded data?

Gridded data in climate science refers to the method of dividing geographical areas into grid cells. Climate models then calculate variables (like temperature or precipitation) for each cell. These models produce outputs that can be visualized as maps, similar to map-based visualizations currently available in Cal-Adapt, that show average conditions across each grid cell at a given time. However, it’s important to note that these grid cell averages may differ from actual observed conditions within each cell, especially in areas with complex topography (e.g., mountains) or in urban settings where microclimates or localized effects (e.g., urban heat islands) can strongly influence the local climate. It is important to note that in the WRF data sets available on AE, a 9 km grid cell is not an aggregate of the corresponding 3 km grid cells for that location; rather the 9 km data is a unique, dynamically-downscaled run of the GCM that is different from the unique, dynamically-downscaled 3 km runs. This independent approach allows a

wider region to be simulated by the WRF model at 9 km, and better spatial resolution to be simulated over the state of California at 3 km.

What is downscaling?

The grid cells in most GCMs are very large – they range between 50 and 300 square kilometers. This coarse resolution is sufficient when scientists are studying climate on the global scale, but it is not as useful for adaptation and planning purposes, where data users need to understand climate change on smaller scales. Present-day climate varies greatly from region to region in California, and future climate is expected to vary accordingly. However, that detail is lost in coarse GCM outputs, where all of California may be represented by just a few large grid cells. To be able to plan for the future, higher-resolution projections of future climate need to be produced. Climate scientists therefore use various models and statistical techniques to “downscale” global climate model outputs to finer, more useful spatial scales (Figure 1).

The data available on the Analytics Engine is from several GCMs that were downscaled to grid cell sizes of 3 km by 3 km, at their finest resolution. This data is available via two different downscaling methods. The first set of available data is dynamically downscaled data from the Weather Research and Forecasting model (WRF), a numerical weather prediction model that simulates weather by using the coarser scale global climate model outputs as boundary conditions for its simulations. The second set of available data is statistically downscaled data from a hybrid statistical-dynamical technique called Localized Constructed Analogs (LOCA2-Hybrid). This method uses past climatological observations to add fine-scale detail to GCM output. The generation of this California-specific, high resolution data was supported by the California Energy Commission (EPC-20-006) and performed by the Scripps Institution of Oceanography (LOCA2-Hybrid) and University of California Los Angeles (WRF). The References section contains links to methods, data sets, and state-level data justification memos associated with these downscaling techniques.

Figure 1: This figure depicts the resolution difference in precipitation between the raw GCM output at a coarse resolution (left) and the fine-scale LOCA2-Hybrid downscaled output (right), showcasing how the additional granularity now depicts California climate more accurately. Pierce et al. 2018

What climate projections and GCMs are on the Analytics Engine?

The Analytics Engine hosts climate projections from 15 GCMs. GCMs are usually named after the research center responsible for the model's generation and maintenance. For example, the GFDL-CM3 model is run by the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Geophysical Fluid Dynamics Laboratory (GFDL).

Each GCM has strengths and shortcomings in how it depicts conditions for a place or a specific aspect of the climate. As a result, climate change analysis is usually best informed by use of the full range of possible model values. Using multiple models and ensemble members will help a data user capture all probable future climate conditions and produce statistical summaries across different models. Tools on the Analytics Engine have been designed to help users investigate spread across models and understand how to characterize the range of possible futures for their metric, region, and time period of interest.

How are climate models validated?

To get a sense of how reliable a model is, climate data users may want to know how well a given climate model has performed. This exercise is commonly referred to as “model validation.” Climate models are typically validated by modeling the historical climate and then comparing this modeled historical climate to the observed historical climate. Observations of the historical climate come from a variety of sources: weather stations, satellites, and aircraft. If the modeled historical climate accurately recreates the observed historical climate record, the climate model is often considered valid.

Climate models can also be put through a series of standardized diagnostic tests to see how skillfully they perform as compared to other validated models, especially with regard to how they generate phenomena observed in paleoclimate records. This practice is referred to as model intercomparison. A common intercomparison test inputs an instantaneous increase in carbon dioxide to four times pre-industrial levels and diagnoses the results of each model. Another common test is a gradual, steady increase in carbon dioxide concentrations until four times pre-industrial levels are reached. To learn more about the diagnostic tests that were used to determine which climate models to downscale for California's Fifth Climate Change Assessment, please refer to [Krantz et al. 2021](#). For additional details on the credibility evaluation process, see the question “How can users assess the credibility of the Analytics Engine data for their contexts” in the Guidance on Using Climate Data in Decision Making section.

What is bias correction?

While GCMs do a good job of capturing the big-picture behavior of global climate, they still contain some systematic biases (such as being consistently too hot in desert regions, or too cold in high elevation terrain). Multiple approaches are used to adjust for these biases, but all rely on data from a historical period to calculate the magnitude of the systematic offsets compared to observed historical values. Those offsets are then applied to future projections. Some bias correction approaches distinguish between aspects of the climate differently, for example applying different systematic offsets to cold periods and warm periods by adjusting each quantile separately to preserve the changes in the distribution of values that a model may project (quantile- based bias adjustment).

On the Analytics Engine, all LOCA2-Hybrid data is bias-corrected: the statistical downscaling process includes a bias-correction step. Some of the dynamically downscaled WRF data is “a priori” bias corrected, meaning that a monthly average bias adjustment was applied before the WRF downscaling procedure, however further bias correction may be needed for some applications. Please refer to the References section for academic publications and state-level data justification memos that contain additional details on bias correction approaches. For additional details on which type of bias corrected data to use in your analyses, see the question “The Analytics Engine hosts two types of downscaled datasets: WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid. Which dataset is most appropriate for a user’s application/context?” in the Guidance on Using Climate Data in Decision Making section.

What historical data are available on the Analytics Engine?

Three types of historical climate data are available in the Analytics Engine data catalog: a set of historical weather stations, and two gridded historical observation products. The hourly historical station observations from a select number of weather stations across California and Nevada are available from the [HadISD archive](#). The first historical gridded product is the historical reconstruction from the [ERA5](#) reanalysis, which uses a variety of historical weather and ocean observations to recreate past atmospheric conditions on an hour-to-hour basis. The ERA5 product on the Analytics Engine was downscaled to a 3 km resolution using the [WRF model](#). The second set of gridded historical data comes from the GCMs run specifically over the historical period (1980-2014). These historical climate time series should be interpreted as possible realizations of a historical climate, but do not attempt to precisely capture actual historical weather patterns. The historical period of GCMs is useful for applications such as calculating the difference between a historical baseline and projected future conditions under different global emissions scenarios.

How are greenhouse gas emissions incorporated in climate models?

What is an emissions scenario?

The main driver of human-caused climate change is the emission of carbon dioxide and other greenhouse gases into the atmosphere. These greenhouse gases trap heat in the atmosphere and cause global temperatures to increase over time. Atmospheric warming in turn leads to other changes throughout earth systems. How much the climate changes in the future depends in large part on the amount of greenhouse gas emitted now and going forward, as well as upon changes in anthropogenic aerosols and land-use. However, since the greenhouse gas emissions and these other factors depend on a variety of different social, political, and economic factors, it cannot be certain how they will change. Nonetheless, scientists can use estimates of these changes to generate scenarios that can drive future climate projections.

Previous generations of climate data used Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) to define plausible greenhouse gas, aerosol, and land-use change scenarios (e.g., RCP 8.5). In the newest generation of models, the international community has adopted new pathways, called Shared Socioeconomic Pathways (SSPs). Compared to RCPs, SSPs provide a broader view of what ‘business as usual’ might look like given different global societal changes, demographics, and economic factors (for further discussion of how SSPs were developed and how they compare to RCPs, check out the [Carbon](#)

[Brief explainer](#)). The Analytics Engine includes climate models for three future scenarios: SSP 2-4.5, a “middle of the road” scenario where emissions continue around present levels through mid-century and then decline; SSP 3-7.0, where emissions rise steadily through the end of the century; and SSP 5-8.5, a “burn it all”, rapid warming scenario where current emissions levels double by 2050.

EMISSIONS TRAJECTORY	DEFINITION	DESCRIPTION	OUTCOME
SSP2-4.5	4.5 watts per meter squared of radiative forcing in the year 2100	Emissions continue at present levels to mid-century and then decline	2.7°C warmer at end of century
SSP3-7.0	7.0 watts per meter squared of radiative forcing by the year 2100	Emissions roughly double from current levels by 2100	3.6°C warmer at end of century
SSP5-8.5	8.5 watts per meter squared of radiative forcing by the year 2100	Emissions roughly double from current levels by 2050	4.4°C warmer at end of century

Table 1: Three of the common greenhouse gas trajectory scenarios hosted on the Analytics Engine.

What are global warming levels?

The global warming levels (GWL) framework provides an alternative approach to assessing climate impacts, as compared to a time- or scenario-based approach. A user can tailor their analyses to a specific amount of global warming, such as 2°C or 3°C, rather than to a particular time period like mid-century or end-of-century (i.e., 2100). This method has gained traction in international policy frameworks, including the [Paris Agreement](#) and the [6th IPCC Assessment Report](#) because it isolates the uncertainty of regional climate responses from other variables, such as emissions trajectories and the rate of global climate response to greenhouse gas concentrations associated with scenario-based approaches. By using GWLs, a greater number of high-quality simulations can be included in regional assessments, even if some models have higher-than-likely [climate sensitivity](#). The GWL approach allows a data user to conduct a more comprehensive analysis by incorporating simulations that accurately represent atmospheric variability but may otherwise be excluded.

For example, consider two simulations: simulation A and simulation B. In an SSP framework under the SSP2-4.5 scenario, a data user might initially consider only simulation A because simulation B is designed only for the SSP5-8.5 scenario. This prevents them from incorporating any regional climate information from simulation B into their analysis. Instead, by employing a GWL framework, a user can examine how each simulation depicts regional climate at specific warming levels, such as 2°C. This approach allows both simulations A and B to be included in the analysis, assuming that each reaches 2°C of warming at some point in their projection. Thus, the GWL framework allows users to enhance their understanding of

climate projection insights beyond simulation A alone. This approach also helps identify when the world is likely to reach a particular level of warming, and provides a robust framework for characterizing the risk of climate extremes and making informed policy decisions. For additional details on how to use GWLs in an analysis, see the question “Why does the Analytics Engine have projections for different Global Warming Levels (GWLs)?” in the Guidance on Using Climate Data in Decision Making section.

What are sources of uncertainty in climate projections?

Climate projections involve several sources of uncertainty that are integral to understanding and interpreting future climate scenarios. Model uncertainty stems from variations in how different GCMs are structured and how they simulate complex climate processes. These models, developed by various research institutions, may produce divergent results due to differences in their mathematical formulations and assumptions about physical phenomena. Scenario uncertainty arises from projecting climate impacts under different global emissions scenarios, such as varying levels of greenhouse gas emissions. This uncertainty reflects an inability to predict future societal choices and policies that influence emissions trajectories. Internal variability comes from the inherent randomness of certain climate processes, such as the timing and intensity of phenomena like El Niño events. Which of these three uncertainties is most important depends on how far into the future climate projections are needed. Internal variability (i.e., unpredictable weather) dominates for periods less than 10 years, model uncertainty (i.e., which model is best) dominates between 10 and 40 years, and scenario uncertainty (i.e., what people and societies choose to do going forward) is the biggest source of uncertainty for periods longer than 40 years.

Despite the uncertainties inherent in modeling future climate, they do not invalidate climate data; rather, they represent the complexity and range of potential future outcomes, and ultimately illustrate the critical importance of policy decisions and how they will determine the magnitude of future climate changes. Climate modelers actively work to reduce model errors through improved model physics, increased computational power, and ensemble modeling techniques that aggregate results across multiple models. For additional information on how to examine uncertainties when conducting climate data analyses, see the question “How can users examine uncertainties in climate data?”, in the Guidance on Using Climate Data in Decision Making section.

Guidance on Using Climate Data in Decision-Making

This page and the sub-pages Using Climate Projections in the AE and Census Tracts offer Analytics Engine data users a set of guiding materials on the most appropriate ways to use climate data for decision making. It includes an explanation of why such guidance is important and provides answers to specific data-related questions that users commonly have. These guidelines can be utilized by any technical or semi-technical data user to better understand the Do's and Don't of working with climate data in the Analytics Engine. By understanding how to effectively integrate climate data into sectors such as energy, municipal planning, natural resource management, and public health, data users can better anticipate and mitigate the impacts of climate change.

Topics covered in this article:

- How can climate data **inform decision making**?
- How should **guidance on climate data** be used?
- Acknowledgements and Citation

How can climate data inform decision making?

Characterizing changing climate conditions is vital for planning and adaptation. Many sectors and communities are grappling with a growing need to use climate data to anticipate and plan for near- and long-term changes. By assessing the range of possible future conditions under a changing climate, communities can proactively plan for actions that can reduce the impacts of climate change and safeguard lives, livelihoods, and landscapes for decades to come.

The historical and future climate data available on the Analytics Engine can be used to analyze a variety of questions related to climate risks for an agency, community, or region. For such analyses, climate data is often used in combination with other qualitative and quantitative data, such as socioeconomic data, information on institutional capacities, local knowledge, etc. For instance, investor-owned electricity and natural gas utilities in California are required to undertake Climate Adaptation and Vulnerability Assessments. These assessments rely on climate as well as other types of data to identify the populations, infrastructure, and natural systems that are at risk of climate impacts, and to evaluate the utilities' ability to adapt to such risks.

For an introductory primer on using climate information in risk and impact assessments, users can refer to this [Guidance published by the White House](#). Users can also peruse this comprehensive [Climate Data Users Guide](#) developed by the [Electric Power Research Institute](#) (EPRI) which provides a fundamental understanding of the various aspects of using climate data. EPRI's guide includes details about key concepts such as climate models, downscaling, choosing projections, and sources of historical and future climate data. Other valuable sources are also listed in the Analytics Engine website's References page. Definitions of key terms are available on the Analytics Engine Glossary page.

How should guidance on climate data be used?

Using projections of future climate to inform decision making is an inherently complex process. The science on climate change is continuously being improved and updated, and new datasets and tools for analyzing climate data are actively being developed. Policy and regulation are also evolving to better integrate future climate information, but are faced with difficult questions about how to do this in effective and rigorous ways. Developing a suitable approach for using climate projections depends on several factors, including: the climate-related question that a user wants to answer, the decision that is being made with the climate data, the type of data that is available for the region and decision-context, regulations or mandates for data use, users' technical capacities to work with climate data, users' limitations for handling large datasets, users' risk tolerance, planning timeframes, compatibility of the climate data with other data or frameworks that the user is working with, etc.

Due to this highly contextual nature of climate data use, there can be no one-size-fits-all guidance for how climate models and data should be used to answer specific planning or management-related questions. To this end, the Analytics Engine has undertaken a co-produced and deliberative process that is rooted in practice, regulation, and science, to develop a more flexible set of guiding materials. The following sections will offer context-specific answers for how to use the data available in the Analytics Engine. However, the onus will ultimately always be on the user to identify the best approach for data use within their specific context. It is critical that climate data users incorporate guidance that is based in scientific best practices, such as what is outlined below, to ensure the integrity and appropriate interpretation of their analyses. As climate data and related policies are updated, guidance on data use will also necessarily evolve. Therefore users' approaches to climate data should be flexible and adaptable to improvements over time. For further specific questions, please reach out to analytics@cal-adapt.org.

For detailed guidelines on appropriate use of climate projections in the Analytics Engine, please see the Using Climate Projections in the Analytics Engine page.

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Using Climate Projections in the Analytics Engine

Below are answers to some common questions about climate data that the Analytics Engine users may encounter. It is recommended that users review these answers before they use the data or tools in AE. These answers are not meant to be prescriptive but rather to provide a framework to think through some of the choices that a user may have to make. Key references have been linked throughout the section, but additional materials are also available on the References page. Users should also review the Glossary page for definitions of key technical terms.

The Analytics Engine hosts two types of downscaled datasets: WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid. Which dataset is most appropriate for a user's application/context?

The dynamically downscaled [WRF](#) dataset and the hybrid downscaled [LOCA2-Hybrid](#) dataset were developed to emphasize different strengths of the two downscaling methods and provide users with distinct dataset options. However, the two datasets differ in several important ways. Therefore, before deciding which dataset to use, users should review the hyperlinked data memos above and this [data catalog](#), which provide fundamental information about the datasets, as well as the downscaling methods, uncertainties, and credibility of the data. To provide one illustrative example of how these datasets can differ – although both datasets provide downscaled climate projections over California at 3-km grid spacing, WRF has hourly data and more variables but for a much smaller set of GCMs, only one SSP, and only one ensemble member. LOCA2-Hybrid data is available for fewer variables at daily resolution but provides projections from many more GCMs, multiple ensemble members, and often for three SSPs. Additional information on WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid downscaling approaches can be found in journal articles linked in the [References](#) page.

In general, choices between these two datasets may be based on:

- 1) **Data fit** - i.e. whether the datasets have the variables, temporal and spatial scales, and SSPs that fit the user's application context
- 2) **Sampling needs** - i.e. whether the user needs to sample widely across models and ensemble members
- 3) **Consistency** - i.e. whether there user needs dynamical or physical consistency among different climate variables
- 4) **Bias correction** - i.e. whether the user needs a specific type of bias corrected data

Broadly, users should first map the key characteristics of both datasets, and determine if one or both have the specific types of information (scales, variables, models, SSPs, etc.) that are essential for a given context or application. For most applications that need daily data within California, the LOCA2-Hybrid dataset provides a wider range of models, ensemble members, and SSPs. The WRF dataset is useful in cases where users need hourly data, WECC (Western Electricity Coordinating Council) wide data, a larger set of variables than the LOCA2-Hybrid dataset provides, or dynamically consistent variables. Dynamically consistent variables are variables within a dataset that are internally consistent and reflect the realistic physics of the climate system, because they are generated from a model that forces variables to be consistent with each other. This ensures that relationships between variables obey real-world physics. For example, temperature and dew point temperature in a dynamically consistent dataset will always behave realistically - dew point will never be higher than air temperature. This consistency is important for accurate climate and weather analysis, especially when studying how different variables like wind, humidity, and precipitation interact. For example, for a WECC-wide analysis that requires hourly wind data the WRF data might be the only viable option, because WRF offers hourly wind data at a 9-km resolution that covers the WECC region. For examining the return period of daily temperature or precipitation extremes (i.e. 1-in-X- events) in California, the LOCA2-Hybrid dataset might be more appropriate since it enables a wider sampling of possible outcomes. In this case, users might also choose to simultaneously examine the WRF dataset, to see if and how results look across the two datasets (see next question).

If both WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid datasets are appropriate for a specific context, can a user use both datasets?

Both WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid are credible datasets, however they differ in how they were developed. For example, the datasets differ in how they were bias-corrected and how some of the physical variables such as wind or precipitation were computed. Therefore, there is not an easy apples to apples comparison between the two datasets, and they cannot be readily combined together. However, **it may be beneficial (and appropriate) to look at both WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid data in tandem but as separate datasets.** For instance, if a user wants to understand how certain extreme events will change in the future, they can examine the detailed dynamics of a single extreme event within the hourly WRF data while also separately examining the distribution of similar events within the much larger set of LOCA2-Hybrid projections.

Because of the differences in the two datasets, it is not advised to ‘combine’ WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid into a super ensemble dataset without additional data processing. If users do indeed find it necessary to combine WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid data, they should first consult with a climate science expert on the type of additional data processing that might be essential to make the two datasets comparable with one another. For example, users may need to ensure that the *bias correction* approaches that have been applied and the computation of physical variables such as wind or precipitation are comparable across the datasets. Also, since some of the same *model runs* have been downscaled using both WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid methods, the issue of double counting the same run would need to be addressed.

The Analytics Engine hosts a-priori bias corrected as well as non-bias corrected WRF data - which one should a user choose?

If users determine that the WRF dynamically downscaled dataset is most appropriate for their application, **it is recommended that they choose the a-priori bias corrected models** [i.e. MIROC6 r11i1p1f1, TaiESM1 r1i1p1f1, EC-Earth3 r1i1p1f1, MPI-ESM1-2-HR r3i1p1f1, EC-Earth3-Veg r1i1p1f1]. These models will likely be the most appropriate option for energy sector applications due to their ability to produce more realistic representations of regional climate than the non-bias corrected WRF models.

Detailed analyses of the non-bias corrected WRF data have shown that they generate results for precipitation, temperature and snow that do not seem to be physically plausible. These non-bias corrected models might still be useful for some advanced applications where users only want to examine the degree of change in the projected data (i.e. change between modeled future and modeled historical conditions) without using absolute values. In this case, users should consult with a climate science expert to carefully factor the implications of the biases in the data into their analyses and results. Users can also review [this](#) bias correction memo and [this manuscript](#) that describe the benefits of bias-correction in WRF data. Additional documents on bias correction are available on the Analytics Engine References page.

How should users choose among the large number of models and/or ensemble members available in the Analytics Engine?

The Analytics Engine [data catalog](#) shows the total number of models and ensemble members from both WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid datasets that are available to users. Broadly, the WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid datasets include several models, and LOCA2-Hybrid has multiple ensemble members for a select few models. Both the WRF and LOCA2-Hybrid datasets come from GCMs that have been pre-selected based on a rigorous skill evaluation of how well they capture key characteristics of California's climate ([Krantz et al., 2021](#)).

Once users have selected a dataset, it is generally recommended that they examine as many models and ensemble members as possible to develop the most complete picture of the range of plausible future outcomes. The Analytics Engine has tools and functionalities that allow users to more easily work with a larger number of models than was previously feasible for the energy sector.

However, there may be certain instances where selecting a smaller number of model runs is necessary (e.g. time series data applications). How a user undertakes this type of sub-selection will depend on the type of climate data application (including the variable, location, and scale of analysis) and the user's ability to process large amounts of data. In cases where it is necessary to select a smaller set of model runs, **users must first perform a preliminary exploratory analysis on the full suite of available data within the Analytics Engine to determine the appropriate set of models and ensemble members for their specific context.** During the exploratory analysis, it might be useful for users to determine if, for their specific application, they care more about **(1) sampling across a range of potential outcomes, or (2) gaining a statistical understanding of (changing) extreme weather events.** While choosing between these two different options is not ideal and is always limiting, there are cases where such difficult trade-offs might need to be made based on practical considerations.

- 1) For cases where it is determined that a range of outcomes are needed, the users' preliminary analysis could entail a **ranking exercise** to characterize all the available model runs for the range of outcomes for the region, timescale, and primary variable(s) of interest (e.g. characterizing model runs from hottest to coolest, or wettest to driest, or based on the change signal in the models). Users can then sub-select a set of model runs to represent the median, mean, and/or either tail of the distribution, depending on which aspect of the distribution is most relevant to their application. If the goal is to select a plausible range of outcomes, then it may not be necessary to distinguish among models and ensembles. If calculating a mean, median, or some other statistical property of the model distribution, though, users should be mindful of how models with different numbers of ensembles are weighted.
- 2) For cases where it is determined that a statistically robust understanding of changing extreme weather events is required, **it is recommended that users avoid sub-sampling to the extent possible**. Extreme event analyses require large ensembles of climate data because these events are often poorly sampled within a single climate model run (a 1-in-100 year event may only occur once in a given ensemble run). Properly understanding the statistics of such extremes requires large ensembles so that there are enough instances of rare events to understand their properties and frequencies. **A user's preliminary analysis should then entail an assessment of both the internal variability and model uncertainty of the entire dataset**. This is because both these types of variability are important for extreme event analyses. *Internal variability* can be examined in the Analytics Engine as the differences among ensemble members from each individual model (i.e. as intra-model variability), and *model uncertainty* can be examined as the differences between various models in the dataset (i.e. as model-to-model variability or intra-model variability). The availability of multiple ensemble members for some models hosted in the Analytics Engine makes it possible to conduct extreme event analyses for each individual model, and to distinguish how different models represent changing characteristics of extreme events. After comparing across models to see how similarly or differently they represent the internal variability, users can then choose models and ensemble members accordingly. If a user still finds it necessary to sub-sample the models, they should perform the aforementioned analyses of the two types of variability for all the Analytics Engine models that have multiple ensemble members. Users should then cross-check the inter-model spread of their chosen sub-sample with the inter-model spread of the broader dataset to check if the full range of outcomes is captured in their sub-sample.

The default setting in many Analytics Engine notebooks is to provide outputs that span all models and ensembles. Users can use the tools in the Analytics Engine to examine both the internal variability and model uncertainty (see example applications [here](#)). Model sub-selections can also be done through the Cal-Adapt Data Download Tool or the API.

What are General Use Projections (GUPs) and can they be used?

While it is always recommended for users to examine as many models and ensemble members as possible, Analytics Engine also hosts a set of "General Use Projections". These five LOCA2-Hybrid model runs [ACCESS-CM2 r1i1p1f1, MPI-ESM1-2-HR r3i1p1f1, EC-Earth r1i1p1f1, FGOALS-g3 r1i1p1f1, MIROC6 r1i1p1f1] have been pre-selected to reasonably capture a range of future outcomes for a limited number of commonly used climate variables, scales, and SSPs. If users are unable to perform context-specific

preliminary analyses as suggested in the previous question and/or are less comfortable working with large amounts of data, the GUPs can provide a **minimum set of model runs to start with before more sophisticated analyses can be done.**

Users should **review [this short memo](#)** for details on how the GUPs were identified and what ranges of outcomes they span (and do not span). Broadly, the GUPs were evaluated for SSP 370 and 2045-2074 (mid-century) changes relative to the 1950-2014 historical period. This was done for selected variables including temperature (change in statewide average annual daily Tmax, degree F), precipitation (change in statewide average annual precipitation, % change), and wind (change in statewide average annual wind speed, % change). In the assessments, the five selected GUPs were able to reasonably capture the range of projected changes for the above-mentioned precipitation and temperature metrics. Future changes in wind speed projected by these GCMs varied quite a lot by location in the state, therefore users who require changes in wind at specific locations should evaluate a broader set of models for their specific location of interest rather than relying solely on the reduced set of general use projections.

Limitations of GUPs: Since GUPs only represent a minimum set of starter projections, they are limited in their scope, and users should exercise caution while drawing conclusions from this sub-selection.

While the GUPs attempt to cover a range of variability for a limited set of pre-determined metrics, it cannot be guaranteed that these model runs will necessarily cover the appropriate range for every user-relevant outcome, i.e. for different time periods, SSPs, regions, and/or variables/metrics. Particularly for applications which involve examining extreme events, the GUPs may not be appropriate, as they may not be able to reasonably capture the full range of extremes. Therefore to the extent possible, it is recommended that users rely upon a larger number of models and ensembles, or conduct their own preliminary analyses to determine which models are needed to capture the appropriate range of plausible outcomes for their specific contexts (as recommended in the model selection question). It is worthwhile to reiterate that existing and forthcoming tools of the Analytics Engine will make working with larger amounts of model runs much easier for users, and therefore users will be able to make use of the full suite of data rather than relying on limited sets of projections.

What temporal scale should users consider?

Temporal scale considerations for users often include four key choices **(1) temporal resolution of the data (hourly or daily), (2) sampling window (number of years of analyses) (3) temporal aggregations (whether and how to average across years of analyses) (4) timeframe (historical, earlier-21st, mid-century, end-century)**. The data and tools in the Analytics Engine allow a user to work with different options for these four choices. Note that these choices have big implications for the size of the data and computational time required to perform analyses. Therefore choices need to be made thoughtfully based on the type of application and potential tradeoffs, i.e. choosing the finest temporal resolution of data might limit the ability to work with longer sampling windows or a larger number of models (if data size is an issue). A user can also conduct preliminary analysis within the Engine's server to examine the implications of these different choices before a decision is made on the temporal scale of the data to be downloaded for further use.

(1) Temporal Resolution

In the AE, depending on the type of data and variable of interest, a user can select between hourly or daily resolution data or pre-aggregated data at daily or monthly scales ([refer to this Analytics Engine data table for more details](#)). Users' choice about the temporal resolution of the data should be informed by the temporal nature of the climate hazard of interest and how it interacts with the user's system and planning process. Overall, **the broad recommendation is for users to identify specific temporal aspects of their application, start coarsely with some preliminary analyses, and then work towards larger sets of data with finer resolutions**. For instance, if users are working with broader trend analysis, changes in central tendency, or seasonal questions, where very specific temporal characteristics are less relevant, they may be able to work with data at daily scales or even pre-aggregated monthly, seasonal, or annual scale data. However, if the application or process involves a daily or hourly model, or if an *8760* analysis is needed, then the user will likely need to work with the higher resolution data. Generating a *Typical Meteorological Year (TMY)* is another example where hourly data may be required for a long climatological period. See the [TMY methodology notebook](#) on AE.

Additionally, if a user is looking at applications or hazards where a certain temporal characteristic (e.g. time of day or the diurnal pattern of data) is of critical importance, then the choice of daily versus hourly data can make a big difference to the results. For instance, examining wildfire risk in the afternoons, hourly exceedances for parking lot design, storm surges, or Santa Ana winds may need hourly or sub-hourly data, whereas examining the recurrence of long-term droughts might not require as fine resolution data (i.e. it may be okay to trade off finer resolution data in exchange for the ability to include a larger number of years in the sampling window).

(2) Sampling Window

Often the choice of an appropriate sampling window is determined by the type of planning or modeling processes that a user is interested in. **It is important to note that longer time windows (i.e. 30+ years) are better able to sample key modes of variability that affect California**, e.g. a 30 year sampling window is needed to capture a reasonable number of El Niño or La Niña cycles, as well as positive and negative Pacific Decadal Oscillations. In addition, some applications like Extreme Value Analyses require at least 30 years of simulation to appropriately pull event maxima. While it is possible to select and examine shorter sampling windows within the AE, users need to be aware that these windows might not adequately represent the modes of variability, and therefore may not be fully representative of the various hazards that might impact their systems (i.e. there is a possibility of missing out on key hazards). If users have to choose a sampling window that is less than 30 years, it is recommended that they use as many models and ensemble members as possible in their analysis. Using data with many different initial conditions and perturbations enables a better representation of different forms of natural variation over a shorter sampling window, than a single model and ensemble member.

(3) Temporal Aggregations

When analyzing data at certain resolutions and sampling windows, some applications may require further temporal aggregations (e.g., for input into other models, or for developing summary statistics or graphs for reports). The tools in the Analytics Engine allow users to analyze events or metrics at a finer

scale within the engine's servers, and then aggregate and download (or further analyze) the data at a coarser scale. For instance, users can evaluate certain heat wave metrics at a fine scale within the engine (e.g. use hourly data to examine total hours of heat index above 90 degrees F). Users can then choose to temporally aggregate the resultant derived heat wave data more coarsely before downloading (i.e., total daily/weekly hours of heat index above 90 degrees F, or daily max heat index) without losing the quality of information. In this manner, the Analytics Engine enables users to examine heat waves at a fine scale using hourly data, without having to download the entire suite of hourly data from every model. Some fine-scale metrics (such as heat index) are already pre-aggregated in the Analytics Engine (some of these pre-aggregated metrics can be found [here](#)).

Broadly, it is recommended that the temporal averaging (if necessary) be done at the end, once the temporal variability and distribution have been examined and considered within the Analytics Engine server. For example, upon examining hourly versus more temporally aggregated data, it was found that for energy demand forecasts, it is more appropriate to calculate demand for each hour and then average or summarize the demand outputs across several years. This was found to be more appropriate than calculating energy demand from the average over a day or over several years, since energy demand varies non-linearly with temperature and other factors. Examples of how to work with temporal aggregations of hourly data depending on desired metric are demonstrated in AE's [Heat Index](#) notebook and the [Annual Consumption](#) notebook.

(4) Timeframe

How to choose a timeframe for analysis (whether to analyze climate impacts for mid-century, 2070, end-of-century, or any other period) is one of the most common questions that users have. Users often need to align their timeframe choices with their planning horizon and/or with the lifetime of the asset/infrastructure under consideration. However, climatic changes, as well as the impacts and risks that stem from these changes, could be non-linear and increase at a more rapid rate towards the end of the century. Hence, near-term timeframes might not always provide a holistic picture of long-term risk and impacts, particularly for the higher SSPs. For instance, if peak load forecasting is analyzed only until 2050, it might not provide a good understanding of the risk that might ensue post 2060. **Therefore, when feasible, users should consider the evolution of risk over longer periods of time (e.g. 2070, end of century, etc), and then break up the analysis into shorter time windows that better align with their planning horizons, asset lifetimes, or other application-specific considerations.** Such longer-term analyses may be essential to better understand how decisions or actions may need to scale over time, particularly for climate impacts that are likely to change at a much faster rate after mid-century (e.g. sea level rise). It can be noted here that using *Global Warming Levels* (GWL) as an alternate framework can help to overcome some of these challenges (see question on GWLs below), as this framework is more suited to adaptive planning.

What spatial scale should users consider?

Spatial scale considerations for users often include three key choices **(1) spatial resolution of data (the size of grid cell or data at a point location), (2) spatial extent (the area over which data is analyzed) (3) spatial aggregations (whether and how to aggregate over a larger geographic area, such as counties or hydrological units, HUCs).** Similar to temporal scales (see above question), the data and tools in the

Analytics Engine offer different options for these choices. Given that these choices have big implications for the size of the data and computational time required to perform analyses, **it is recommended that users conduct preliminary analyses within the Analytics Engine server to examine these implications before deciding on the spatial scale of the data to be downloaded or synthesized for further use.**

(1) Spatial Resolution

The first spatial scale choice that climate data users often need to make is whether they need data at a point location or if they are able to work with gridded data. In general, if users want to examine a hyper-local issue (e.g. a point-based asset such as a substation) or if they are working with a model or workflow that is parameterised or dependent on a particular weather station, then they may need to use point location data. However, if users are looking at regional climate responses, then gridded data might be most appropriate.

Point location data: Climate models do not automatically output data at point locations. However, **the Analytics Engine has developed a Weather Station [Localization](#) notebook that allows users to generate data at particular locations for which the user has historical data.** Hourly temperature data is also available on the Analytics Engine at 32 select weather stations that were identified as important for the energy sector for the LOCA2-Hybrid dataset. If users are looking to examine a point location that does not have available historical data, then they would need to conduct a qualitative assessment using the finest resolution gridded data for the nearest gridcells to the point location to determine how representative the grid cell average is of the specific point location.

Gridded data: If users choose the LOCA2-Hybrid dataset, this is offered only at 3km x 3km resolution. However if users choose the WRF dataset, this data is available at 9km x 9km as well as 3km x 3km resolution. **When choosing a spatial resolution, the broad recommendation is that users should first identify the specific spatial aspects of their application, and then conduct preliminary analyses in the Analytics Engine servers to compare between different resolutions.** Users should evaluate the tradeoffs (information that is gained or lost) by choosing different resolutions. For instance, if users have data size or computational constraints, choosing very fine resolution data may restrict their ability to examine a greater number of model runs or larger spatial extents. It can also be noted that higher resolution spatial data is not always better or necessary for every analysis. Many informed decisions and investments can be made by using lower resolution data that considers more models and plausible future outcomes. When conducting preliminary analyses, users must also be aware of the spatial heterogeneity/variability (topographic, climatic, or other) within the region that they want to assess. Finer resolution data could provide greater benefits for regions that are spatially heterogeneous (e.g. areas of complex terrain or regions that transition quickly from water to land) as compared to regions that are more spatially homogeneous (e.g. the Central Valley). It can be noted that many areas in California are characterized by a high degree of spatial variability in weather, topography, and the human dimensions of infrastructure and demographics. Therefore, depending on the region and climate variable under consideration, the spatial heterogeneity within a grid cell (and also across adjacent/nearby grid cells) might be large. Overall, the goal should be to select the most appropriate spatial resolution for the context, that also allows for a broad range of model runs to be included.

(2) Spatial Extent

The choice of spatial extent is often dependent on the risk or climate hazard that users want to analyze, and/or the question they are trying to answer. The spatial extent needs to be large enough to properly analyze the climate issue under consideration. For instance, to analyze the impacts of a heat event on system-level planning, a user may need to examine the entire regional extent where the impacts of the heat events may occur. For other specialized analyses, such as evaluation of streamflow, sector-specific domains (or spatial extents) such as watersheds can be applied to gridded climate data. **Here, care must be taken to create a rigorous workflow which carefully considers edge cases where a gridcell may be only partially included in a polygon area** (In the AE, functions such as [rioxarray clip](#) have been used to better examine some of these issues). Users should also note that conducting hyper-local spatial analyses (e.g. using census tracts in urban areas) may require specialized approaches that are highly dependent upon a given question or application, and therefore are beyond the scope of this general guidance document.

(3) Spatial Aggregation

Some applications may require aggregating data across a larger spatial area (such as a county or a watershed) before it is downloaded or examined for further use (e.g. for developing synthesis graphs or summary numbers for reports). However, users should note that some of the quality of the information may be lost when spatially aggregating across different locations or gridcells. For instance some aggregations (such as averaging over large spatial areas) could lead to missing out on specific distributional impacts for different communities, which might have equity implications. Therefore, users need to be aware of the types of impacts that they might miss out on when aggregating across gridcells. If aggregation is necessary, it is recommended that users do not default to spatial averaging. Instead, **users should first examine climate impacts without aggregation, and then aggregate at the end, once the spatial variability and distribution have been examined within the Analytics Engine server.** For example, finer scale analyses of population-weighted heat exposure can be first assessed at the gridcell level and then aggregated to a county level for reporting, after the variability has been examined. In such cases, users should consider reporting other distributional statistics over the aggregated areas, such as the spatial variability within the county.

The homogeneity of the climate hazard over the spatial area that a user is aggregating over is also very important. For instance, aggregating heat metrics over a largely homogenous plain area might be less challenging than aggregating precipitation over a topographically diverse area. In addition, users must exercise further caution when aggregating over gridcells for assessments of extremes, such as for *extreme value analysis*. In extreme value analyses, if multiple gridcells from a climatologically diverse area are averaged, there is a chance of accidentally biasing the results to the most extreme value in the area and/or missing an extreme of interest. As in several of the previous questions, users will need to make an informed decision about the right balance between performing a good quality and rigorous analysis versus one that is computationally light and technically feasible within their context.

How should a user use reference periods in the Analytics Engine?

What is a reference period?

To evaluate climate impacts from climate model outputs, it is often helpful to calculate the difference between future conditions and a historical reference period. This difference is called a “change signal” or a “delta signal”. To compute this change signal an appropriate future timeframe and reference period must be chosen. The reference period is often called a baseline climatology. Both the future period and the reference period should be long enough to characterize the average climate conditions and year-to-year variability during a given historical period. It is typically recommended that the future and reference periods be 30 years long. For consistent comparisons, the future period and reference period should also generally be the same length as each other.

Depending on the goal of the analysis, reference periods can be chosen to approximate present day conditions or some other point in the past (e.g. 1950 to 1980). The choice of reference period can have a significant impact on the apparent magnitude and characteristics of the change signal, so care should be taken with this selection. The discussion below will help inform decisions about reference periods for different types of analyses in the Analytics Engine.

Why use reference periods?

There are two major reasons to use a reference period to calculate a climate change signal rather than directly using future values from a climate model. First, specifying a reference period frames the severity of future climate conditions in a meaningful context. This means that relative metrics like percent change from a historical period can be calculated. Second, it helps avoid biases in climate models. By calculating changes relative to a baseline from the same model, biases in the underlying climate state are cancelled out. The result is a better estimate of the change signal that can be directly compared between different climate models.

Reference periods for time-based analyses

When examining future climate conditions using time-based analyses, any time period can be chosen as a reference period, provided it is sufficiently long to characterize the mean climate. Scientific best practices recommend 30 years, but 20-year reference periods may be appropriate in a limited number of application-specific cases. For the WRF simulations in the Analytics Engine data catalog, the earliest year simulated is 1980, so 1980-2010 is a standard baseline climatology. For LOCA2 simulations, data extends back to 1950, so earlier climatologies can be calculated if desired.

Note on later reference periods: The climate simulations in the Analytics Engine data catalog use a ‘historical’ scenario for the years 1950-2014, and split into separate simulations that follow different SSP scenarios for years 2015 and onward. It is possible to define a reference period that extends beyond 2015 (e.g. 1995-2025), but it requires combining data from the historical scenario and a chosen SSP simulation.

Reference periods for global warming levels

When examining future climate conditions using a global warming levels approach, the selected reference period should also be defined as a global warming level. This will help prevent adding uncertainty to the calculated change signal. In essence, if a time-based reference period (e.g., 1980-2010) is used as the baseline for a warming level (e.g., 2.0°C) inconsistencies can be introduced as not every simulation warms at the same rate. We illustrate this in the figure below.

Using warming levels as the future target and the reference period ensures that consistent and comparable change signals are calculated for each simulation. Because global warming levels are agnostic to SSP scenarios, you do not have to choose a scenario when using a warming level as a reference period.

How selecting GWL reference periods can influence results

- **Consistent Periods:** Comparing conditions at 2.0 °C of global warming to conditions at 0.8 °C of warming creates a consistent change signal (1.2 °C of global warming) across simulations and scenarios. This ensures that results focus on the change signal and comparative impacts.
- **Inconsistent Periods:** Comparing conditions at 2.0 °C of global warming to time-based reference of 1980-2010 results in comparing a different amount of warming in each simulation. In this example one model has warmed by 1.1 °C while the other has warmed by 1.6 °C, adding additional uncertainty to the change signal.

The Analytics Engine has three global warming levels designed specifically to be used as reference periods, summarized in the table below:

	Global Warming Level	Approximate equivalent time range for 30-year climatology
Historical baseline	0.8 °C	1987 - 2016 (center year 2002)
Recent historical	1.0 °C	1995 - 2024 (center year 2010)
Present day	1.2 °C	2005 - 2034 (center year 2020)

Estimated center years and associated 30-year climatologies for the standard reference GWLs in Analytics Engine. Timing of GWLs is calculated using [data from the IPCC](#).

For each reference period, the approximate equivalent time range is determined using the IPCC’s aggregation of the historical climate record and estimated timings for future warming under the SSP 3-7.0 Scenario, as shown below for the 0.8 °C warming level.

Estimate of the year the world reached 0.8 °C of warming. Figure produced by the Cal-Adapt: Analytics Engine based on [data from the IPCC](#).

Additional considerations for selecting global warming level reference periods

The default reference warming level on the Analytics Engine is 0.8 °C, and is recommended unless a particular use case requires a different choice. Because 0.8 °C is the earliest warming level that can be defined with this dataset, it provides the clearest change signal to future warming levels like 1.5°C. The 1.0 °C and 1.2 °C warming levels are useful when a warming level closer to present-day conditions is needed, or if the approximate timeframe of these warming levels is more consistent with an existing planning process.

Depending on the length of the climatology that is needed, some simulations from EC-Earth3 and EC-Earth3-Veg are not available at the 0.8 °C and 1.0 °C warming levels. These simulations have warmer historical temperatures, and therefore exceed 0.8 °C or 1.0 °C of warming before the start of the downscaled simulations. When 0.8°C and 1.0°C warming levels are used within the Analytics Engine, either individually or as a part of a change signal, we have ensured simulations from EC-Earth3 and EC-Earth3-Veg are not retrieved. If including these simulations is important, using the 1.2 °C reference period will ensure that data from all simulations is retrieved.

Note on pre-industrial reference period

In line with the IPCC definition, Global Warming Levels are defined as warming relative to pre-industrial conditions (years 1850-1900). This time period defines the 0 °C warming level, but this time period is not an option for a reference period for regional climate impacts on the AE.

There are two important reasons we don't use 0 °C of warming as a reference period:

1. Significant changes have occurred in the climate between the pre-industrial period and present day. From a planning perspective, pre-industrial conditions are not familiar, and not very useful in the context of modern infrastructure and societal needs.
2. The downscaled climate simulations in the Analytics Engine only extend back to 1980 (WRF) or 1950 (LOCA2), so downscaled data at 0 °C of warming is not available. The lowest global warming level that can be defined with our downscaled data is 0.8 °C

Why does the Analytics Engine have projections for different Global Warming Levels (GWLs)? How is this approach different from using emission scenarios (such as RCPs or SSPs)? How can users use GWLs for their analyses?

Until the last few years, it was most common to assess climate projections at a particular time period, such as mid-century or end-of-century, and for different emission scenarios (RCPs or SSPs). However, it is becoming increasingly common to assess climate projections at different levels of warming, for example how regional climate change might look like in a world that is 2°C or 3°C warmer on average than pre-industrial levels. Key national and international climate assessments such as the IPCC AR6 and the NCA5, are using the warming level framework for several reasons. This [blog](#) and slides [11-17 of this presentation](#) explain in detail why the warming level framework has been preferred.

Broadly, one of the main reasons for using GWLs rather than a time-based approach, is that **there is less certainty around the rate (timing) of climate change than the range of possible temperature outcomes at a given level of warming** (see this Analytics Engine [blog](#) for a visual representation). When using a time-based approach to plan for a specific target year(s), users are often forced to pick projections from

a particular emissions trajectory. This limits the overall sample size of model runs and therefore reduces the ability to holistically characterize future outcomes, specifically extremes and rare events. On the other hand, **the GWL framework allows users to avoid choosing among the different emissions trajectories and hence increases the sample size of model runs that they can use.** That is, to evaluate climate impacts in a 2°C world one must combine the regional projections from all available simulations, regardless of the emissions scenario and regardless of when they reach 2°C of global average warming. This larger sample size provides users with a greater ability to holistically examine risks and, in particular, to better characterize risks from extremes. The approach also allows for isolation of the different sources of uncertainty in regional climate responses, which lends itself to a more adaptive management approach (see this Analytics Engine [blog](#) for more details). Overall, the GWL framework allows more robust climate change analyses, as summarized in the [IPCC AR6](#) “...robust projected geographical patterns of many variables can be identified at a given level of global warming, common to all scenarios considered and independent of timing when the global warming level is reached.”

The AE’s Warming Level Notebooks allow users to easily examine regional climate impacts for a specific global warming level. In these notebooks, users can first identify target warming levels (e.g. 2°C or 3°C global warming), and then calculate the regional climate response of interest for those GWLs with the largest possible set of model runs. These notebooks also have functionalities that allow users to examine the median time period when a given warming level might be reached (i.e. go from GWL to time estimates), thereby also providing a time-based estimate for planning purposes. This [example application](#) can help users get familiar with the functions of the notebook. Similar to the recommendations on choice of timeframes, it is also recommended that users do not fix-in on any one warming level, but also undertake exploratory analyses at additional warming levels. In particular, including a higher-end warming level may be beneficial for capturing potential nonlinear impacts of climate change, which can enable adaptive planning.

How should a user choose between Global Warming Levels and a time-based approach to planning?

Determining whether to use GWLs versus time- or scenario-based approaches will depend on the goals of the analysis, and/or external requirements for planning. As a starting point for making these decisions:

- If planning occurs around discrete future time periods that use a climatology (i.e. averaging conditions over a 30-year period), it is recommended that a GWLs approach is used.
- If planning relies on viewing a long-term trend (e.g. through the end of the century) as a continuous time-series, it is recommended that a time-based approach is used.

The sections below provide more detail on making decisions between these approaches.

When should I choose GWLs for my planning?

Using Global Warming Levels (GWLs) for planning comes with some distinct advantages over a traditional time-based approach:

- Avoiding additional uncertainty about warming trajectories due to [hot models in CMIP6](#).
- Improving statistical robustness by incorporating climate simulations from all scenarios.

- Enabling an adaptive, scenario-agnostic planning approach that focuses on critical thresholds.
- Providing consistency with climate change analyses from the [Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change \(IPCC\) AR6 report](#), the [Fifth National Climate Assessment](#), and [recommendations from the California Public Utilities Commission \(CPUC\)](#).

For these reasons, it is recommended that GWL approaches are used with CMIP6 data whenever possible. This is particularly true when a climate analysis needs to be conducted around a future time period, such as 30 years in the middle or end of the century (i.e. a future climatology).

For California’s Investor Owned Utilities, the [California Public Utilities Commission specifically requires planning around global warming levels of 1.5 and 2.0 °C](#) when completing a Climate Adaptation and Vulnerability Assessment (CAVA).

Using GWLs in the Analytics Engine is as straightforward as using time-based climate data. An overview of how to easily retrieve data on GWLs along with a detailed methodology of how this is implemented is available on our [methods page](#). The table [on this page](#) can help you choose GWLs that correspond to a relevant future period for your analysis, and communicate results in situations where time-based planning may be more familiar.

When is time-based planning recommended instead of GWLs?

Despite the advantages of GWLs, time-based data may be more appropriate for certain approaches, such as:

- Using a continuous time series to visualize or analyze a long-term climate trend (e.g. through the end of the century).
- Comparing the timing or intensity of climate impacts between different scenarios explicitly (e.g. comparing SSP 3-7.0 to SSP 5-8.5).

Additionally, climate impacts that exhibit a significant delay in response to global temperature increase or are sensitive to the rate of warming are difficult to analyze with GWLs. Examples of these impacts are sea-level rise, glacial melt, and coastal processes driven by land-sea temperature differences.

Finally, when using time-based climate data it is important to keep in mind that increased uncertainties about future warming and climate impacts arising from [the “hot model problem”](#) will become more pronounced towards the end of the century.

For additional information on GWLs, please see the [Methods page](#) on the AE.

How can users assess the credibility of the Analytics Engine data for their contexts?

All of the downscaled data available in the Analytics Engine comes from GCMs that have been pre-selected based on a rigorous skill evaluation of how well the models capture several relevant characteristics of California’s climate. These GCMs were shown to perform well for both process-based as well as local climate metrics. The models were able to simulate the key physical processes and patterns that strongly influence the hydrological cycle and extreme weather in California, and they were also able to capture local climatic patterns such as annual and seasonal patterns of temperature and precipitation. This sort of state-level GCM assessment is unique, and lends broad credibility to the data

that is being hosted in the AE. More details on how the GCMs were evaluated and selected are available in [Krantz et al., 2021](#).

Although all the models in the Analytics Engine have been shown to perform well at capturing California’s climate broadly, this does not necessarily mean that all models perform equally well for any specific sub-region within California or for any specific metric (particularly ones that were not evaluated within the GCM selection process). In such cases, users may want to additionally understand whether and to what extent the data being used is credible for their specific region, metric, or application. Here, an additional level of credibility analysis could be of interest to a user. However, the approach for such additional user-driven GCM evaluations is still an evolving area of research and experimentation that scientists and practitioners are collectively trying to figure out.

For additional credibility analyses, users may first want to qualitatively assess whether and to what extent the GCMs represent the key underlying physical processes that are relevant to the phenomenon or region of interest. This can be done using existing studies or literature on the GCMs. Then they may want to quantitatively examine the historical performance of the models or dataset, for the metric that is of interest. Upon such analyses, users might consider three key questions: (1) Are the class of models available suitable/appropriate for the specific *use-case*, climate phenomenon, or variable of interest? (2) Is there a need to differentiate between the various models based on their historical performance?, and (3) Should some models be avoided (or culled) for specific regions, variables, or applications? However, these are nuanced questions that require advanced analyses that cannot be predicted or easily identified.

One instance where an additional credibility evaluation might be useful to users, is for cases where specific wind variables are needed. Wind is often a tricky variable to capture well in climate models due to its extremely local characteristics, which can be affected by local buildings, trees, hills, etc. A user may want to validate that the data they are using reasonably captures the distribution of wind extremes in a given location of interest before proceeding to analyze changes in that metric in the future. (It can be noted that such a validation analysis might need access to specific observed data sets to compare to, which can be difficult to obtain for variables like wind). When such fine-scale features are being examined, it is possible that only a subset or even none of the models represent the phenomenon of interest very well. In this case users may want to rule out certain models or might determine that the available data is not appropriate for their application. Ruling out models should be balanced with considerations about sampling (see the model selection question), so that users ensure that they do not overscreen models and miss out on plausible and realistic outcomes.

Overall, it is worthwhile to reiterate that user-centric credibility evaluations are still an evolving matter in both science and practice. Sub-selections or culling of models based on very specific credibility assessments need to be done carefully and in consultation with climate science experts on the best course of action.

How can users examine uncertainties in climate data?

The goal of the climate projections in the Analytics Engine is not to provide a singular prediction of the future but rather to allow users to examine different plausible future outcomes. The data in Analytics Engine allows users to explore a range of potential future climate projections using different datasets,

models, and emission scenarios. There is inherent variability within this range due to the natural fluctuations within the climate system (*internal variability*), variation in climate responses of different models (*model uncertainty*), as well as uncertainty in future emissions of greenhouse gases (*scenario uncertainty*). More details on types of uncertainty can be found in AE's About Climate Projections and Models page, the Glossary page, and also in the "[Choosing Climate Projections](#)" section of the [EPRI Climate Data Users Guide](#). Overall, users should be aware that there are uncertainties both in the amount of future greenhouse gas emissions as well as how the climate system will respond to these emissions. However, these uncertainties do not invalidate the usefulness of climate data for adaptation, but rather represent a necessary part of planning for climate hazards and risks. Further, climate modeling processes are continually improving to provide better representations of the climate system.

Although all three sources of uncertainties are important to understand, the relative value of each type of uncertainty depends on the type of application, context, and time-period of decision-making. Therefore, disentangling the different sources of uncertainty and examining how each of them evolve over time, can help energy sector users better characterize and work with the specific uncertainties that are most useful for their context. For example, internal variability might be more important for planning processes that focus on the near-term (e.g. the Integrated Energy Policy Reports, IEPR assessments), whereas scenario uncertainty might be of greater value to consider for end-of-century planning (e.g. long-term distribution planning).

In the AE, users can use the internal variability notebook, the model uncertainty notebook, and the forthcoming emissions uncertainty notebook to perform some of these uncertainty analyses. In addition, specific recommendations related to appropriate consideration of uncertainty are also included within some of the previous answers, such as model selection, spatial scale selection, and temporal scale selection.

How have these guidelines been developed?

These guidelines have been developed as part of the CEC-funded project EPC-20-007 with support from Amazon Sustainability, titled "[A Co-Produced Climate Data and Analytics Platform to Support California's Electricity Resilience Investments](#)". The main aim of this project is to provide customized data, advanced analytics, and powerful cloud computing resources to support climate-informed planning and research to improve resilience in the electricity sector. The project uses a "co-production" approach, where the data, tools, analytics, and guidance documents (including these guidelines) are collaboratively developed alongside key energy sector climate data users and a diverse group of scientists.

The initial set of questions that have been answered here were developed based on interviews and focus groups with energy sector climate data users. In these interviews, users identified the most common challenges that they encounter while using climate data for planning and adaptation purposes. The initial answers to these questions were drafted by three climate scientists and two social scientists who are part of the Analytics Engine project team. These preliminary answers were informed by the latest climate science literature as well as first-hand knowledge of the issues faced by climate data users. The answers were then edited and refined through a rigorous and iterative process that spanned several months, and incorporated the perspectives of a wide-range of data users (such as energy utilities, state agencies, energy consultants), scientists (including climate scientists, climate data producers, social scientists, energy sector specialists), as well as software tool developers. This process included gathering both

written and verbal feedback through deliberative focus group discussions. In particular, the project team from CEC's EPC-20-006 project "[Development of Climate Projections for California and Identification of Priority Projections](#)" provided extensive feedback on several versions of the document.

What are the limitations of these guidelines?

- These guidelines provide users with a scientifically-grounded starting point for how to use climate data to answer real world questions. However, the onus is ultimately on the user to identify whether, and to what extent, these broad guidelines are sufficient for their specific context. There may be complex or nuanced cases where these guidelines either do not apply or are insufficient.
- These guidelines are only applicable to the climate projections data that are hosted in the AE. While some of the key takeaways could also be more broadly relevant, their applicability to other regions or planning contexts has not been examined.
- Some of the recommendations in the guidelines require access to computing resources, tools, and notebooks, such as those in the AE.
- These guidelines were developed based on the perspectives of a diverse but limited set of experts and their understanding of the usability of LOCA2-Hybrid and WRF datasets. As the credibility and actionability of this data is further examined by other scientists and practitioners, some of the guidelines might need to be re-considered.
- These guidelines have not yet been empirically tested/examined in terms of where (and for which applications) they work and where they do not. As users work through these guidelines, if there are suggestions for improvements please reach out to analytics@cal-adapt.org.
- Finally, these guidelines are not static. They are meant to be updated continuously over time as practical, scientific, and regulatory understanding of climate change evolves and as new data emerges.

Overview of Heat Metrics for Energy Sector Planning

Background

Understanding how increasing temperatures affect asset performance and simultaneously drive demand for gas and electricity are essential parts of planning in the energy sector. Temperature alone is often not enough to capture the complex relationship between weather conditions, human comfort, and heating and cooling demand. A variety of heat metrics are used to better quantify these relationships, build reliable forecasts of energy demand from meteorological conditions, and enable climate-informed planning for energy sector assets. The Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine offers built-in functionality for many of the most common heat metrics, and the flexibility for planners to customize or implement their own. Here we explain key differences between heat metrics and direct users to relevant tools and resources both within the Analytics Engine and externally to support their use in planning applications.

Heat Index

Overview of heat index

Heat index is a metric that combines air temperature and relative humidity to quantify the human-perceived temperature ([Steadman 1979](#)). It generally captures the fact that humans feel warmer in humid conditions, and uses a series of formulas and assumptions to quantify this effect. Because heat index is a better predictor of human comfort than temperature alone, it is a valuable tool for predicting energy demand for cooling on hot days. Heat index only uses temperature and humidity as inputs (not solar radiation or wind), and as such it is best used as an estimate of the apparent temperature in the shade. It is not useful for capturing wind-chill or other effects at low temperatures ([NWS Heat Index Statistics](#)).

Calculating heat index

The modern approach to calculating heat index relies on a multiple regression analysis developed by Rothfus in 1990 to capture the complex relationship between temperature, humidity, and perceived temperature ([NWS Heat Index Equation](#)). The Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine utilized NOAA's implementation of the Rothfus regression formulas for heat index, which uses additional adjustments for days with particularly high or low relative humidity ([AE Heat Index Applications Notebook](#)). Because these heat index formulas are only well defined for days above 80 °F, the Cal-Adapt calculation returns the original temperature below this threshold.

For days that do not need an additional correction, the heat index is calculated as:

$$\begin{aligned}
 HI = & -42.379 + 2.04901523 \cdot T + 10.14333127 \cdot RH - 0.22475541 \cdot T \cdot RH \\
 & -0.00683783 \cdot T^2 - 0.05481717 \cdot RH^2 + 0.00122874 \cdot T^2 \cdot RH \\
 & +0.00085282 \cdot T \cdot RH^2 - 0.00000199 \cdot T^2 \cdot RH^2
 \end{aligned}$$

Where T is air temperature and RH is relative humidity.

Note: "NOAA Heat Index" is available as a [derived variable](#) in the Analytics Engine data catalog, with an [example notebook](#) to demonstrate its usage.

Wet Bulb Globe Temperature

Overview of wet bulb globe temperature

Wet bulb globe temperature (WBGT) is a metric that estimates heat stress in direct sunlight by using measurements of temperature, humidity, wind speed, and solar radiation ([Budd 2007](#)). It is used extensively as a measurement of heat hazards for humans, particularly for outdoor workers ([OSHA Technical Manual](#)). The use of several meteorological variables allows it to capture a variety of effects that influence the physiological response to high temperatures, but it has limited utility in cold

temperatures. Similar to heat index, WBGT is a useful metric for connecting meteorological conditions to energy demand from cooling.

Calculating wet bulb globe temperature

Wet bulb globe temperature was originally formulated to utilize physical measurement devices that take a reading of wet-bulb temperature, dry-bulb temperature, and globe temperature. However, methods have been developed to compute WBGT from meteorological data from weather stations or climate models ([Liljegren et al. 2008](#)) ([Dimiceli & Piltz](#)).

Note: Wet Bulb Globe Temperature is not currently implemented as a pre-defined metric on the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine, but it can be derived from variables in the Analytics Engine data catalog using either the method from [Liljegren et al. \(2008\)](#) or the [NWS's Dimiceli-Piltz algorithm](#).

Effective Temperature

Overview of effective temperature

Effective temperature is a heat metric that captures the cumulative effects from several days of temperature measurements. It uses a weighted sum of temperature measurements from the current day and some number of previous days ([Elexon BSC Glossary](#)). This makes it a useful metric in the energy sector for capturing how heat retention in buildings can impact demand for heating or cooling over subsequent days, and it has been used as a predictor of gas consumption under various formulations ([National Grid Gas Demand Forecasting Methodology July 2020](#)).

Calculating effective temperature

Effective temperature is calculated as a weighted sum of temperature across some number of consecutive days, but the specific number of days and their respective weights can vary based on the specific application. Within the energy sector, Elexon uses a three-day formula with a weight of 0.57 for today's temperature, 0.28 for the prior day, and 0.15 for the day before that ([Elexon BSC Guidance Notes](#)). National Gas uses a recursive formulation, with the effective temperature defined as 50% of the current day's actual temperature and 50% of the previous day's effective temperature. Other formulas are used by utilities and energy planners based on their specific regions and applications ([Azari et al. 2012](#)) ([Ashouri 1993](#)). Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine uses a formulation of effective temperature based on the National Gas weighting scheme, with a four-day range ([climakitae Indices](#)). This version represents an industry standard with a proven track record in gas demand forecasting.

The formula used by the Analytics Engine for effective temperature is:

$$T_{eff} = 0.5 * T_{today} + 0.5 * T_{eff, yesterday}$$

Where T is daily average air temperature, and T_{eff} is effective temperature, and the recursive formula uses four days of backwards looking temperature data.

Note: Effective temperature is available in the Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine data catalog as a pre-calculated [derived variable](#). Other formulations of effective temperature can be calculated from daily or hourly temperature data from climate projections in the Analytics Engine data catalog.

Cooling and Heating Degree Days

Overview of cooling and heating degree days

Cooling and heating degree days (CDDs and HDDs) are heat metrics based on the number of days above or below a specific temperature threshold, and by how many degrees the temperature exceeded that threshold. Degree days are designed to quantify how outdoor temperature drives demand for indoor heating and cooling ([NWS Heating and Cooling Degree Days](#)). These metrics have broad use throughout the energy sector for energy demand forecasting, establishing building standards, and prioritizing investments in improved heating and cooling technology ([EIA Degree days](#)). Rather than being a metric with one fixed definition, degree days are a flexible method that can be customized with thresholds and temperature metrics that suit a particular region or application.

Calculating HDDs and CDDs

For a given day, the number of degree days is calculated as the number of degrees that the day's temperature is above (or below) a set threshold ([NWS Heating and Cooling Degree Days](#)). Degree days are always positive, and days that do not exceed the threshold are counted as zero degree days. The threshold is set based on an estimate of when heating or cooling of a building is needed. Thresholds can be different for heating and cooling degree days and/or vary based on the region or application. A standard threshold of 65 F is often used as a default. It is also possible to calculate CDDs or HDDs using a derived temperature metric like heat-index, wet bulb globe temperature, or other temperature metrics ([Staffell et al. 2023](#)).

$$CDD = (T - T_{CDD \text{ threshold}}) \quad \text{if } T > T_{CDD \text{ threshold}}$$

$$HDD = (T_{HDD \text{ threshold}} - T) \quad \text{if } T < T_{HDD \text{ threshold}}$$

Note: The Cal-Adapt Analytics Engine provides tools to calculate CDDs and HDDs from climate simulation data, including customizable temperature thresholds and a [sample notebook](#) to demonstrate their use.

Choosing the right heat metric for your application

There may be multiple heat metrics that are appropriate for use in different contexts, and/or combinations of them that are suited to a particular energy planning applications. Choosing the right metric and its formulation will depend on a user's needs, and may require testing and numerical

comparisons to determine which one performs best in a particular region and application. What follows are some general insights into the differences between each metric, and examples of the type of considerations that a user might walk through to choose between them.

Heat index and **wet bulb globe temperature** are both metrics with specific scientific definitions. Their formulas combine multiple meteorological variables to produce a perceived temperature that is relevant to humans and energy demand. They are both targeted specifically at understanding heat stress on high temperature days, and are useful for understanding extreme heat health risks and the need for shelter and active cooling.

Given their similarities, choosing between them may be based on:

- The need to specifically capture the effects of direct sun exposure that is included in WBGT, or the need for an estimate of shaded temperature that heat index provides.
- The availability of data, with heat index only requiring two commonly available variables.
- The need for consistency with other organizations, for example the NWS use of heat index in weather forecasts, or OSHA use of WBGT for occupational hazards.

In contrast, **effective temperature** and **degree days** are both customizable methods for combining temperature measurements over multiple days to estimate their impact on cooling and heating demand. These methods do not have a universal definition, and can be tailored to use a weighting scheme or threshold that matches a particular application. They are also both used in the context of understanding cooling demand on hot days as well as heating demand on cold days.

Effective temperature can be used as a replacement for daily temperature when examining the relationship between temperature and electricity demand. In this context, it can capture the lagged response of energy demand due to heat retention in buildings and cumulative heat stress for humans. The choice of a specific weighting scheme may depend on empirical data for this relationship in a particular region.

Degree days are more often used to summarize bulk demand for heating and cooling in a region on a monthly or annual basis, making them particularly well suited for summarizing long-term changes. The choice of threshold temperature for CDDs and HDDs has a large impact on the numerical results. When standardization and comparability of results to other sources is important, utilizing a standard 65°F threshold can be advantageous. When making more specific energy forecasting decisions, incorporating additional information about regional behavior or past data about the relationship between temperature and energy demand can be important for developing context-specific results.

Getting Data at the Census Tract Level

Many planners, agencies, and community organizations use census tract data because it can enable targeted planning, policy, and programmatic decision making at a local level. It is therefore common for practitioners to ask whether climate model projections can be translated to census tracts to support their analyses, particularly those that may require overlays with demographic information. However,

climate models do not produce data at census tract resolution. This introduces important risks and limitations when attempting to map gridded climate data onto these boundaries.

How the Analytics Engine Supports Use of Climate Data at Census Tract Levels

To support needs for climate data at a census tract level, the Analytics Engine (AE) team has developed a Python-based tool called clip within the project's Python toolkit [climakitae](#) that allows users to clip gridded climate datasets to census tract polygons. For more details on how to use this clip tool with "clip": "<geoid>" or "clip: [<geoid>, ...]", please navigate to the "Processor Example 5: Clipping to Boundaries" section in the [Data Access Notebook](#).

The following guidance describes the key risks and technical challenges associated with conducting census tract-level analyses with climate data. It aims to provide guidance on which information census tract-level estimates can and cannot reliably provide.

The Analytics Engine team's goal is not to deliver authoritative "census tract climate datasets", but to provide transparent, reproducible tools that allow users to explore climate data responsibly. The [climakitae](#) census tract clipping tool is intended as a learning and analysis aid, paired with guidance like this page to help users understand the assumptions, risks, and appropriate interpretations involved in using climate data at a census tract level.

Challenges Using Climate Model Data for Census Tract Analysis

The climate models used in the Analytics Engine produce data on regular grid cells of a fixed 3 x 3 kilometer size. US census tracts, by contrast, are irregularly shaped statistical areas within a county whose size varies widely depending on population density; they are generally designed to represent 1,200 to 8,000 people ([U.S. Census Bureau, 2022](#)). In population-dense areas like downtowns, census tracts can be very small (such as a few city blocks), while in rural areas, a single census tract can occupy a large portion of the county. This difference in census tract size can make translating gridded data onto a census tract-level tricky.

Climate models do not produce data at census tract resolution. Most datasets used in the Analytics Engine are produced on [equal-area grid cells](#) that are much larger than many urban census tracts, and much smaller than rural area census tracts. This fundamental mismatch creates several technical challenges that users should carefully consider:

- **Spatial mismatch and grid-scale representation:** In dense urban areas, multiple census tracts may fall entirely within a single model grid cell. In these cases, the same climate variable value (e.g. temperature) will be assigned to several census tracts, even though real-world conditions may vary meaningfully across neighborhoods due to the built environment, land cover, or proximity to water (Figure 1). For dynamically downscaled datasets such as WRF, each grid cell value represents conditions at the grid cell's center point and is assumed to be representative of the broader grid area (3km x 3km). Sub-grid variability (such as sharp elevation changes, coastal gradients, or urban features) is not explicitly resolved. As a result, when census tracts are smaller

than a grid cell, or intersect only a portion of one, users should keep in mind that the climate value reflects a modeled approximation rather than conditions everywhere within that area. These tract-level differences are not resolved by the climate model and should not be inferred from the data.

- **Aggregation issues:** Census tracts and grid cells are not a perfect one-to-one match. In rural areas, a single census tract may span many grid cells that differ substantially in elevation, land cover, or climate. Any value summarized across the tract (such as a mean or percentile) will smooth this variability. As a result, a tract-wide average may not be representative of the conditions experienced by most locations within that tract (Figure 2).
- **Coastal census tracts:** In coastal areas, census tracts may intersect grid cells that are partially or mostly over water. For example, the census tract that houses the University of California Santa Barbara includes coastal and off-shore grid cells, which have different temperature characteristics than the adjacent land. When these grid cells are averaged at a census tract level, the resulting values may appear cooler or less extreme than the conditions actually experienced on land. While this issue is not unique to census tracts and reflects a broader limitation of gridded climate data over complex geography, it becomes an especially important consideration when working with climate data at these small spatial scales.
- **Individual grid cells:** For dynamically downscaled datasets such as WRF, each grid cell value represents conditions at the grid cell's center point and is assumed to be representative of the broader grid area (3km x 3km). Sub-grid variability (such as sharp elevation changes, coastal gradients, or urban features) is not explicitly resolved. When census tracts are smaller than a grid cell, or intersect only a portion of one, users should keep in mind that the climate value reflects a modeled approximation rather than conditions everywhere within that area.

Note: Census tract boundaries change over time as populations shift and definitions are updated. The Analytics Engine uses a specific census tract vintage: [TIGER/Line Shapefile, 2020, State, California, Census Tracts](#). Users should be aware that tract-based analyses may not align perfectly with older or newer demographic datasets.

Figure 1. Example of spatial mismatch between a single model grid cell and multiple census tracts within the city of San Francisco, CA. If extracting air temperature for these seven census tracts, each tract would result in the same value, despite actual microclimatic differences within these neighborhoods. Census tracts shown here are: 161.02, 202.02, 167.00, 168.01, 168.02, 162.00, 163.00, San Francisco, CA.

Figure 2. Example of a large rural census tract from the Central Valley into the Sierras spanning multiple climate model grid cells. If extracting a single representative air temperature value for this census tract, the variability of temperatures would be substantially smoothed, and may not accurately represent realistic conditions. The census tract shown here is census tract 1.02, Kern, CA.

Therefore, climate model data that is extracted at the census-tract level should not be treated as representative climate values for that tract. Rather, this data should be viewed as an approximation of the climate, with uncertainty introduced by the size of the model grid and how it represents real-world geography.

Analyses Best Supported by Census Tract-Level Estimates

Using climate data at a census tract-level can be useful for certain types of exploratory or screening-level analyses, particularly when the goal is to understand broad spatial patterns rather than precise local values. For example:

- When identifying general “hotter” or “colder” parts of a region to support high-level prioritization ([Szagri et al., 2023](#)); e.g. cooling demand may be higher for inland census tracts that are relatively warmer than nearby coastal tracts, even if exact temperatures cannot be resolved at the neighborhood scale.
- Overlaying climate indicators with demographic or vulnerability datasets to understand regional patterns or disparities ([McCullagh et al., 2025](#)); e.g. identifying census tracts with both higher projected extreme heat exposure and higher proportions of elderly residents to flag areas where

heat-related health risks may be elevated at a regional scale, without interpreting the values as precise-neighborhood-level temperatures.

- Supporting qualitative or comparative assessments where relative differences matter more than precise magnitudes; e.g. comparing whether one group of census tracts is generally warmer or experiences more extreme heat days than another group (such as inland versus coastal tracts) to inform discussion, screening, or prioritization (rather than to calculate exact thresholds or design specifications).

In these contexts, tract-level climate estimates can help frame questions and guide further analysis, provided their limitations are clearly acknowledged.

Analyses That May Not Be Appropriate at a Census-Tract Level

- The decision requires accurate representation of neighborhood-scale temperatures, extremes, or microclimates ([Fuhrmann et al., 2024](#)).
 - Results will be interpreted as precise predictions for a specific tract, for example, counting the number of days above a critical threshold.
 - The analysis depends on values that change significantly within individual grid cells (for example, coastal versus inland differences).
 - Infrastructure, sizing, or engineering decisions that require higher-resolution information than climate models can reliably provide.
-